

The effect of obtaining conditions on the structure and composition of Cu–MoS₂ coatings upon magnetron sputtering of composite targets

A.Sagalovych, V.Popov, V.Sagalovych, S.Dudnik, A.Dziuba

Joint-Stock Company "FED", 132 Sumskaya Str., 61023 Kharkiv, Ukraine

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The surface morphology and phase composition of the coatings obtained by magnetron sputtering of Cu–MoS₂ composite targets have been studied by X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy and X-ray spectral microanalysis. X-ray diffraction studies of coatings show presence of two crystalline phases, namely Cu with face-centered cubic lattice and CuMo₆S₈ with a rhombohedral lattice. Studies of the surface morphology in Cu–CuMo₆S₈ coatings revealed two types of structures. One of the structures is realized in the form of globular formations, while the second is similar to the structure that had single-component Cu coating. X-ray spectral microanalysis showed that globular formations have higher Mo and S contents in comparison with other type of surface structure. The ratio between these elements is close to that in CuMo₆S₈. However, the Cu content is many times higher than the calculated amount for this compound. This suggests that globular formations are heterostructural where only one of the phases is CuMo₆S₈. Other possible phases in globular formations should be based on copper. The total area of globular formations in the coating increases with an increase in the proportion of MoS₂ in the composition of the Cu–MoS₂ sputtered composite target and strongly depends on the substrate potential.

Keywords: magnetron sputtering, coatings, copper, molybdenum disulfide, Chevrel phases.

Вплив на структуру і склад умов отримання покриттів при магнетронному розпиленні композиційної мішені "мідь — дисульфід молібдену. О.В.Сагалович, В.В.Попов, В.В.Сагалович, С.Ф.Дудник, А.В.Дзюба

Методами рентгенівської дифрактоскопії, растрової електронної мікроскопії та рентгенівського спектрального мікроаналізу вивчено морфологію поверхні, фазовий склад покриттів, що були отриманих магнетронним розпиленням композиційних мішеней Cu–MoS₂. Рентгеноструктурними дослідженнями у покриттях встановлено наявність двох кристалічних фаз — Cu з ГЦК ґратками і CuMo₆S₈ з ромбоєдричною ґраткою. Дослідження морфології поверхні у покриттях Cu–CuMo₆S₈ виявили два типи структур. Одна зі структур реалізується у вигляді глобулярних утворень, друга подібна до структури, яку мали однокомпонентні покриття з Cu. Рентгенівський спектральний мікроаналіз показав, що глобулярні утворення мають більш високий вміст Mo і S у порівнянні з іншим типом структури поверхні. Співвідношення між цими елементами близьке до їх співвідношення у CuMo₆S₈, однак вміст Cu у багато разів перевищує розрахункову кількість для цієї сполуки. Це дозволяє припустити, що глобулярні утворення є гетероструктурними, в яких тільки одна з фаз є CuMo₆S₈. Основою інших можливих фаз у глобулярних утвореннях повинна бути мідь. Сумарна площа глобулярних утворень у покритті збільшується зі зростанням частки MoS₂ у складі композиційної мішені Cu–MoS₂ і сильно залежить від потенціалу підкладки.

Методами рентгеновской дифрактографии, растровой электронной микроскопии и рентгеновского спектрального микроанализа изучена морфология поверхности, фазовый состав покрытий, получаемых магнетронным распылением композиционных мишеней Cu–MoS₂. Рентгеноструктурными исследованиями в покрытиях установлено наличие двух кристаллических фаз — Cu с ГЦК решеткой и CuMo₆S₈ с ромбоэдрической решеткой. Исследования морфологии поверхности в покрытиях Cu–CuMo₆S₈ выявили два типа структур. Одна из структур реализуется в виде глобулярных образований, вторая сходна со структурой, которое имело однокомпонентное покрытие из Cu. Рентгеновский спектральный микроанализ показал, что глобулярные образования имеют более высокое содержания Mo и S по сравнению с другим типом структуры поверхности. Соотношение между этими элементами близкое к их отношению в CuMo₆S₈, однако содержание Cu во много раз превышает расчетное количество для этого соединения. Это позволяет предположить, что глобулярные образования являются гетероструктурными, в которых только одна из фаз есть CuMo₆S₈. Основой других возможных фаз в глобулярных образованиях должна быть медь. Суммарная площадь глобулярных образований в покрытии возрастает с возрастанием доли MoS₂ в составе распыляемой композиционной мишени Cu–MoS₂ и сильно зависит от потенциала подложки.

1. Introduction

Materials based on molybdenum sulfides with copper are useful in a number of fields of science and technology. In addition to their traditional use as a material for tribological purposes, the use of these materials for sensors [1], electrodes for power supplies [2, 3] and a number of other applications is under study. The variety of properties of materials based on molybdenum sulfides with copper and new possible areas of their use gave impetus to a broader study of the properties of such materials and methods of their preparation.

Depending on the field of application of materials based on molybdenum sulfides with copper and its functional purpose, various methods of obtaining such materials can be used, namely chemical, electrochemical, metal Injection molding and some other methods [1–6]. Certain properties of materials based on molybdenum sulfides are determined by their structure and composition, which, in turn, are very sensitive to the methods and conditions of their preparation. Depending on the method and conditions for the formation of materials based on molybdenum and copper sulfides, composite two-phase materials Cu–MoS₂ or compounds of Cu_xMo_nS_{n+1(2)} type or the so-called Chevrel phases, where $0 < x < 3.5$, $n = 2$.

Using the magnetron sputtering method of Cu–MoS₂ composite targets, coatings of the Cu_xMo_nS_{n+1(2)} [7–9] type were obtained. To obtain coatings of different compositions, the ratio of the areas of molybdenum disulfide and copper in the composite target of the magnetron sputtering source was changed.

The coatings obtained in these works were used as an object for studying superconducting properties of this type of compounds and effect of the ratio of the components of this compound on the value of the superconducting transition temperature.

The data on the composition of the obtained coatings were given without indicating the values of the ratio of the areas of molybdenum disulfide and copper in the target of the magnetron sputtering source. In works [10, 11] a coating containing Cu₂Mo₆S₈ sulfides was also obtained by the method of pulsed magnetron sputtering of a composite Cu–MoS₂ target of a special design. The data on the ratio of the components in the coating as well as the ratio of the components in the composite target are not presented by the authors of this work.

Most of the other works on obtaining coatings by the magnetron method based on molybdenum disulfides were focused on studies aimed at increasing the wear resistance of materials based on molybdenum disulfide and maintaining high lubricating properties under conditions of operation in a humid air atmosphere [12–17]. Since Cu has low hardness and wear resistance, metals such as Ti, Zr, Cr, and their solid compounds, as well as Co, V, Fe, Ni and some others were chosen as alloying elements for coatings based on molybdenum disulfides. Thus, there is very little information on the production of coatings by the magnetron method during sputtering of Cu–MoS₂ composite targets of different composition and changes in this connection in the composition of coatings, their structure, as well as the effect of other factors on these characteristics of coatings.

- obtaining coatings based on molybdenum sulfides with copper by the magnetron method when sputtering composite targets Cu–MoS₂ and studying the effect on the structure and composition of the coating of the ratio of the areas of molybdenum and copper disulfide in the composite sputtered target, as well as the substrate potential;
- assessment of the possibility of using the obtained coatings as an alternative to the composite Cu–MoS₂ electrolytic coatings used in the production of JSC "FED".

2. Experimental

The experiments on the production of coatings were carried out in the Avinit M unit of the Avinit [16] automated vacuum-plasma depositing cluster based on upgraded unit UVN 71 equipped with a TORUS 3" HV planar magnetron sputtering source with R601 high-frequency power supply provided by Kurt J.Lesker. MoS₂ target manufactured by Kurt J.Lesker with a thickness of 6.3 mm and a diameter of 76 mm and disc of the same diameter made of copper of the M0 grade were used as target of the magnetron sputtering source. The composite target was represented by sandwich of MoS₂ disk and a copper disk with holes. The holes were located in a circle in the area of maximum target sputtering rate, limited by the radii $R \sim 18$ mm and $R \sim 28$ mm. Using copper targets with a different number of holes, and hence with different ratio of the surface area of the sputtered materials in a composite target, it was possible to obtain coatings of different compositions. High-voltage power supply up to 1.7 kV equipped with arc suppression system was used to ensure the potential on substrate.

Bronkhorst EL-FLOW PRESTIGE FG-201CV flow meter was used to supply process gases into the chamber as well and control and maintain gas flow rate at certain level. KPDR900 vacuum gauge provided by Kurt J.Lesker was used to control the pressure in the chamber. High-purity argon of grade A was used as process gas during the operation of the magnetron sputtering source. The unit is equipped with FTC 2800 thickness gauge provided by Kurt J.Leske in order to control the coating growth rate and determine the coating thickness online. The thickness could also be determined by height of the step formed during the growth of the coating on the substrate, part of which was masked. Under such method for determination of coating thickness, the

height of the steps was measured using measuring station Hommel-Etamic Nanoscan 855 for controlling the roughness and surface contour. X-ray structural studies of the coatings were carried out by means of DRON-2.0 diffractometer in filtered Cu–K α radiation. X-ray diffraction patterns were recorded for phase analysis according to Bragg-Brentano's focusing scheme θ – 2θ within angular range from 10 to 100 degrees. After processing the diffraction patterns and determining the angular position of diffraction peak, the interplanar distance d_{hkl} was calculated using the Wolf-Bragg formula. The size of the coherent scattering regions in the samples (CSR) was determined based on broadening of diffraction lines using the Scherrer formula. The morphology and elemental composition of the coatings were studied using a scanning electron microscope REM-106I with an X-ray energy dispersive analysis system. Qualitative and quantitative analysis of the composition of the samples under study is carried out automatically using special software. The relative error in measuring the mass fraction of an element from 6C to 92U with a sample content of more than 10 wt. % is ± 4 %, with a sample content of 1 to 10 wt.% is ± 20 %, with a content of 0.1 to 1 wt.% in a sample is ± 50 %. The sensitivity threshold of the X-ray energy dispersive analysis system is 0.1 %.

The coatings were applied to substrates made of DIN1,773 steel, which had been subject to surface cleaning after manufacturing using the technology adopted by FED JSC. Before placing the samples in the vacuum chamber, the surface of the substrates was additionally wiped with a coarse calico pad soaked in solvent gasoline in accordance with TU U22340203.001-97 (C2-80/120). After loading the substrates, the vacuum chamber was evacuated to the pressure of $(2.7 \div 3 \cdot 10^{-2})$ Pa. Then Ar was supplied through the flow meter at a rate at which the pressure in the chamber increased to ~ 6 Pa, and a negative voltage was applied to the substrate from a high-voltage rectifier for the purpose of cleaning the surface of the substrate in glow-discharge plasma. The voltage was gradually increased to 600 V and once stable combustion of the glow discharge is reached without micro-arc breakdowns it was kept at this level for 5 min. After the completion of the ion-plasma cleaning of the substrate, the supply of Ar was reduced until the pressure was $\sim 10^{-1}$ Pa, under which the discharge was ignited in

the magnetron with closed shutter. During 5 min of operation of the magnetron, the discharge power was gradually raised to 200 W with a simultaneous decrease in the Ar flow rate until necessary pressure was reached in vacuum chamber, i.e. $(7\div 8)\cdot 10^{-2}$ Pa. The magnetron shutter was opened and coatings were applied on all samples studied in this work for 1 h in this operation mode of magnetron.

3. Results and discussion

Preliminary studies were carried out to obtain coatings by the magnetron method through sputtering only molybdenum disulfide target and copper target in order to determine the growth rate and structural characteristics of such coatings for subsequent assessment of the effect on these characteristics of coatings obtained by sputtering a composite target. Experiments were also carried out to determine the minimum ratio of the surface of the sputtered materials in the composite target, at which the formation of sulfide phases in the coating could be detected by means of used study methods. Carried out studies have shown that such a minimum ratio of the sputtered surface of MoS₂ to Cu in the area of maximum target sputtering rate, limited by the radii $R \sim 18$ mm and $R \sim 28$ mm, is close to 0.4. Based on this fact, composite targets, in which the ratio of the area of sputtered surface of MoS₂ to Cu exceeded 0.4, were used. Considering this fact, composite targets, in which the ratio of the area of the sprayed surface of MoS₂ to Cu exceeded 0.4, were used in further studies.

X-ray diffraction analysis of coatings obtained by sputtering a copper target showed that only single phase, Cu, with an face-centered cubic arrangement is revealed. All the lines of this phase were present. The ratio of their intensities was close to the tabular values, i.e. there was practically no preferential orientation. Lattice spacing was equal to 0.3617 nm, which coincides within the error with the tabular value of 0.3615 nm. The size of the coherent scattering regions (CSRs) was 103 nm. The growth rate of the coating, measured with a thickness gauge and determined using a profilometer by step height, had approximately the same value and amounted to 4.26 $\mu\text{m/h}$ and 4.4 $\mu\text{m/h}$, respectively.

Similar studies for coatings obtained by sputtering molybdenum disulfide target revealed the presence of only the hexagonal MoS₂ phase. The film lines were weak and

wide, suggesting finely dispersed crystal structure. The strongest reflection of this phase is MoS₂ (002) at the diffraction angle 2θ near 14.4 deg was hardly visible due to formation of the texture. The line intensity ratio indicated that the coating had a texture with a predominant orientation of the crystallographic planes (101) parallel to the substrate plane, at which the axis of the hexagon c is tilted by 40 deg to the film plane. The lattice spacing had the values $a = 0.316$ nm, $c = 1.229$ nm, which practically coincides with the table values for the MoS₂ lattice spacing $a = 0.3161$ nm and $c = 1.2294$ nm. The CSR size was 10 nm. The coating growth rate was 2.2 $\mu\text{m/hour}$.

When obtaining complex Cu–Mo–S coatings, two composite targets were used, in which the ratio of the sputtered surface of MoS₂ to Cu in the area of target maximum sputtering rate was 0.44 and 4. Coatings No. 1 were obtained by sputtering a composite target at ratio of the sputtered surface MoS₂ to Cu that was equal to 0.44 and in the absence of potential on the substrate. Coatings No. 2, No. 3, and No. 4 were obtained by sputtering a composite target at ratio of the sputtered surface of MoS₂ to Cu that was equal to 4 and at a negative potential on the substrate of 100 V and 200 V, respectively. The growth rate of coatings No. 1 was 3.25 $\mu\text{m/hour}$ and growth rate for coatings No. 2 was equal to 3 $\mu\text{m/hour}$. The coatings that were deposited on substrates with a negative potential had noticeably slower growth rates. So, for coating No. 3 it was 1.58 $\mu\text{m/h}$, for coating No. 4 it was 1.5 $\mu\text{m/h}$.

X-ray diffraction analysis of coatings obtained by sputtering MoS₂–Cu composite target suggests the presence of two phases regardless of the relative fraction of the copper component in the total area of the composite target and the potential on the substrate. The main phase is Cu with face-centered cubic arrangement. The second phase, the lines of which are much weaker, is the rhombohedral CuMo₆S₈. The X-ray diffraction patterns also showed the lines of steel substrate made of the α -Fe. Table 1 shows the results of numerical processing of diffraction patterns: angular position $2\theta_{max}$, interplanar distance d , intensity I and half-width $B1/2$ for the first five diffraction lines present on diffraction patterns. Table 2 shows the integral intensities of the main reflections on diffraction patterns and the ratio between them for Cu and CuMo₆S₈.

Table 1. Results of numerical processing of a portion of diffraction patterns

No.	$2\theta_{max}$, deg	d , 10^{-1} nm	I , c.u.	$B_{/2}$, deg	Phase
Sample No. 1					
1	41.22	2.188	6	1.05	CuMo ₆ S ₈
2	43.28	2.088	367	0.33	Cu
3	44.40	2.040	26	0.99	α -Fe
4	47.43	1.915	3	0.61	CuMo ₆ S ₈
5	50.29	1.812	18	0.96	Cu
Sample No. 2					
1	40.93	20.203	12	0.81	CuMo ₆ S ₈
2	43.28	2.089	60	0.57	Cu
3	47.62	1.908	10	0.64	α -Fe
4	44.24	2.046	7	1.0	CuMo ₆ S ₈
5	50.34	1.811	17	0.85	Cu
Sample No. 3					
1	40.69	2.215	6	0.90	CuMo ₆ S ₈
2	42.87	2.108	53	0.86	Cu
3	44.10	2.052	29	0.82	α -Fe
4	47.13	1.927	3	1.70	CuMo ₆ S ₈
5	49.80	1.829	9	1.50	Cu
Sample No. 4					
1	40.87	2.206	5	1.06	CuMo ₆ S ₈
2	42.96	2.103	51	0.96	Cu
3	44.30	2.046	21	1.16	α -Fe
4	47.5	1.912	4	0.82	CuMo ₆ S ₈
5	49.60	1.836	6	1.54	Cu

The numerical criterion for the presence of texture is the deviation of the ratio of the intensity of diffraction lines from the values given in the database for a non-textured sample. For copper, the ratio of non-textured sample is $I_{111}/I_{200}/I_{220} = 100/46/20$. From the data shown in Table 2, it can be seen that this ratio practically coincides with the data for sample No. 2. For the rest of the samples, the (111) orientation prevails. The strongest reflection of the CuMo₆S₈ (101) phase at the diffraction angle 2θ near 13.8 was absent in the diffraction patterns, suggesting the presence of a texture for this phase. The ratio of the line intensities suggested that the CuMo₆S₈ compound in the coating had a predominant orientation of the crystallographic planes (131) in parallel to the plane of the substrate. Under such orientation of the planes, the axis of the unit cell c is located at an angle of 15 degrees to the plane of the film. The presence of texture makes it impossible to correctly perform quantitative phase analysis. Numerical criterion that characterizes the

ratio of the phase content may be taken very roughly as ratio of the sums of the integrated intensities $I_{Cu}/I_{CuMo_6S_8}$ of all identified lines of the Cu and CuMo₆S₈ phases. The lower the ratio, the higher the content of the second phase. According to this criterion, the minimum content of CuMo₆S₈ was in sample 1, and the maximum one was observed in sample 2. Samples No. 3 and No. 4 had similar values for the CuMo₆S₈ content. More accurate data on the content of Cu in the coatings were obtained from the results of X-ray spectral microanalysis of these coatings. Thus, Cu content was 98.2 wt.% in sample No. 1, 87 wt.% in sample No. 2, 93.1 wt.% in sample No. 3 and 92 wt.% in sample No. 4.

Determination of the CSR value of the phases present in the coating (Table 3) showed that for Cu its value depends appreciably both on the content of the second phase in the coating and on the substrate potential. For the CuMo₆S₈ phase, CSR value of different coatings differs to a lesser extent. It can only be noted that pres-

Table 2. Integral intensities of the main reflections in diffraction patterns for Cu and CuMo₆S₈ and the relationship between them

α -Fe	Cu				CuMo ₆ S ₈			$I_{Cu}/I_{CuMo_6S_8}$
(110)	(111)	(200)	(220)	$I_{111}/I_{200}/I_{220}$	(131)	(042)	(431)	
Sample No. 1								
24	147	20	10	100/13/7	10	2	0	14.7
Sample No. 2								
5	41	17	9	100/41/22	11	5	3	3.3
Sample No. 3								
22	50	14	4	100/28/8	6	5	1	5.6
Sample No. 4								
23	54	9	4	100/17/8	8	4	0	5.6

Fig. 1. Image of the coating surface of sample No. 1. The arrow indicates the precipitates, which were analyzed by EDX method.

ence of a potential on the substrate and its increase results in decrease of CSR value of this phase, as was the case for Cu phase.

Studies were carried out using scanning electron microscopy and X-ray spectral microanalysis (X-ray spectral microanalysis) in order to determine structural features of the surface of the obtained coatings.

The surface morphology of coating No. 1 differed from the coating obtained by sputtering a copper target, only by the presence of a small amount of precipitates. These precipitates were located mainly along cutter marks on the coating, which reproduced the morphology of the ground surface of the substrate and their size did not exceed fractions of a micron (Fig. 1). Elemental analysis in the area of such precipitates suggests, in addition to Cu, the presence of Mo in the quantity of 1.08 wt.% and S in the quantity of 0.15 wt.%. In the areas of the coating without precipitation, the Mo amount did not exceed 1 wt.%. S was <0.1 wt.%, i.e. threshold sensitivity of the

Table 3. Size of CSR phases disclosed in coatings

Sample No.	CSR size, nm	
	Cu	CuMo ₆ S ₈
1	40	12
2	23	16
3	15	14
4	14	12

system for energy dispersive analysis of X-rays or less. The study of coatings No. 2–No. 4 revealed a strong influence of substrate potential on surface morphology. Fig. 2 shows a view of the surface of the coating No. 2 obtained at zero potential of the substrate.

The coating has a homogeneous polydisperse globular structure with a maximum globule size of ~ 2 µm without reproducing the morphology of the ground substrate surface. The coating was gray. The average amount of Mo in globular formations was 8.81 wt.%, and S was equal to 4.1 wt.%. The ratio of the amount of Mo and S, was 2, 15, which is close to the ratio of these elements in the compound CuMo₆S₈.

The image of surface of coating No. 3 obtained at a negative substrate potential of 100 V is shown on Fig. 3.

The coating had an inhomogeneous structure with globular precipitates that tended to form continuous chains along cutter marks on the coating, and there were also localized precipitates. The structure of this surface was, to some extent, similar to the structure of coating No. 1, not accounting amount and size of precipitates. According to the results of determination of composition of precipitates at points 1 and 2 by the

Fig. 2. Image of the surface of coating No. 2, obtained at zero potential of the substrate.

XRD method, Mo content was equal to 13.37 wt. % and 6.67 wt. %, S content was equal to 4.53 wt. % and 2.3 wt. %, respectively. The ratio of quantity Mo and S is 2.95 at point 1 and 2.9 at point 2. For CuMo_6S_8 of stoichiometric composition, the weight ratio of Mo and S is equal to 2.25. This means that the presence of the CuMo_6S_8 phase in the crystal lattice of this compound suggests the deficit of sulfur atoms. Determination of the composition of the coating in the interval between precipitates at point 3 suggests the presence of Mo in quantity of 6.8 wt.% and S in quantity of 0.52 wt.%.

Surface structure of coatings obtained at a negative potential on the substrate of 200 V took intermediate position between the coatings for samples No. 1 and No. 3 (Fig. 4). The number of precipitates and their sizes were larger than for those of coating No. 1, but smaller compared to coating No. 3.

According to EDX data, the content of Mo was 14.04 wt.% and the content of S was 4.88 wt.%. The size ratio of these elements in the inclusion was 2.88, which is quite close to the value of this ratio in inclusions of coating No. 3. In the interval between the inclusions (point 2 in Fig. 4), the coating contained Mo in quantity of 5.4 wt % and S in quantity of 0.32 wt.%.

Studies of the surface morphology in $\text{Cu-CuMo}_6\text{S}_8$ coatings revealed two types of structures. One of the structures is realized in the form of globular formations, the second does not differ in appearance from the structure that had a single-component Cu coating. There is a definite correlation in terms of quantitative ratio of such structures in the coating and the ratio of the intensities of the reflections $I_{\text{Cu}}/I_{\text{CuMo}_6\text{S}_8}$ on diffraction patterns (Table 2). Based on these facts, it could be assumed that the

Fig. 3. Image of the surface of coating No. 3 obtained at a negative substrate potential of 100 V. Arrows indicate the precipitates and point at which the composition was analyzed by EDX method.

Fig. 4. Image of the surface of coating No. 3 obtained at a negative potential of substrate 155 V. The arrows indicate the precipitates and point at which the composition was analyzed by the EDX method.

globular formations are presented by CuMo_6S_8 compound, and the second structure is Cu, which are recorded during X-ray diffraction analysis of these coatings. However, the data on the composition of these two types of structures do not allow such a conclusion. So, in the composition of the coating No. 2, which had a purely globular structure, besides Mo and S, there was Cu in quantity of 87 wt.%, which was many times higher than quantity of this element in the CuMo_6S_8 compound. Since Mo/S ratio practically corresponded to the wt.% ratio of these elements in the CuMo_6S_8 compound, it can be assumed that globular formations are heterophasic, where one of the phases is CuMo_6S_8 . It is impossible to make certain assumptions regarding the composition of other possible phases in globular for-

mations on the basis of obtained data, except that their base should be copper.

Despite the difference in the methods and conditions for obtaining coatings, the results presented in the work [10] and this paper have several common points regarding the composition and structure of the coatings. Studies in work [10] showed that the surface morphology of the coatings had two types of structures, although their appearance differed from the structures described in this work. Globular precipitates, determined by transmission electronic microscopy, consisted of a mixture of copper crystallites with an average transverse size of ~ 60 nm and sulfide nanoparticles $\text{Cu}_2\text{Mo}_6\text{S}_8$ with an average size of ~ 8 nm. The formations in the form of fibers had a nanocrystalline structure and consisted of the same sulfide nanograins that were present in the form of inclusions in globules. According to EXD data, the globules were present in the quantity of ~ 99 wt.% (Cu), and the rest share was occupied by Mo and S in a ratio of ~ 0.7 . Fibers were equal to 54.74 wt.% (Cu), 30 wt.% (Mo) and 15.26 wt.% (S). Testing such coatings in atmospheric area showed that they have significantly higher tribological properties compared to the matrix material free of sulfide inclusions.

The mechanism of the formation of the CuMo_6S_8 phase, as well as heterostructural formations, observed in this work during magnetron sputtering of composite Cu-MoS₂ targets, is not clear. Minimum required concentration of all the components that make up the compound must be ensured for the formation of such compounds on the condensation surface of the coating. In this case, the minimum required concentration of only one or part of the elements included in the compound can be decisive. When sputtering MoS₂ targets by the magnetron method, the S content in the coatings, as a rule, turns out to be lower than it should be according to the stoichiometry for molybdenum disulfide. A decrease in S content in the coating was also observed upon increase in the temperature of the substrate, an increase in the negative potential of the substrate or the current density on the substrate [19, 20]. This is due to the higher rates of re-evaporation and sputtering of S as compared to Mo.

In the coatings obtained in this work, the weight ratio of Mo to S was not less than 2.15, while for the sputtered target made of MoS₂ this ratio is equal to 1.5. This means that the concentration of S in the flow of

Fig. 5. Set of parts with Cu- CuMo_6S_8 coating.

sputtered target atoms was much higher than in the coating. If we proceed from the assumption that the S concentration on the growing surface is the minimum necessary for the formation of CuMo_6S_8 , then this can be achieved starting only with a certain fraction of MoS₂ in the sputtered target. This is conditioned by the fact that the CuMo_6S_8 compound was found in the coating only after the fraction of the MoS₂ surface in the sputtered composite target increased to a certain value. Due to change in the surface concentration of S, it is possible to explain the dependence of the number of globular formations on the potential of the substrate, which is associated with the presence of the CuMo_6S_8 phase in the coating. It is known that surface scratches are defects with increased surface energy, which makes adsorption of atoms on such defects energetically favorable. This means that the scratches will be in places with an increased concentration of S atoms. Therefore, the preferred formation of CuMo_6S_8 should have occurred precisely on such defects, which was observed in the study of the coating surface.

JSC FED widely uses various types of anti-friction and wear-resistant coatings [18, 21] in the designs of aircraft units. They also include Cu-MoS₂ coatings obtained by the electrolytic method [22, 23]. Magnetron sputtering methods, in contrast to electrolytic ones, are environmentally friendly, low-waste coating methods, which makes their use preferable in industrial processes. In this regard, JSC FED sputtered CuMo_6S_8 coating by magnetron methods with total copper content of 87 wt.% on parts, for which company's technology provide for

deposition of Cu–MoS₂ (Fig. 5). The unit with a set of such parts has passed all trial operations and bench tests without any remarks. This fact confirms the possibility for using Cu–CuMo₆S₈ coating as an antifriction coating in one of the traditionally used field, where sulfide-containing coatings are used.

4. Conclusion

When a composite target is sputtered to a certain ratio of molybdenum disulfide and copper in the resulting coatings, X-ray diffraction studies reveal only Cu with an fcc structure. When this ratio is exceeded in the targets, the presence of two phases is recorded in the coatings. The main phase is Cu with an fcc structure, the second phase is rhombohedral CuMo₆S₈.

Changes in the composition of the coatings recorded by X-ray structural studies are accompanied by changes in the morphology of the coating surface. On the surface of coatings containing the CuMo₆S₈ phase, globular precipitates are recorded, the amount of which correlates with changes in the X-ray diffraction patterns of the relative intensities of reflections from the CuMo₆S₈ phase.

Studies of the elemental composition established a higher content of Mo and S in globular formations on the surface of two-phase coatings. The Mo/S ratio in the globular formations is close to the content of these elements in the CuMo₆S₈ compound. Copper was also recorded in globular formations in an amount that was many times higher than its content in a compound of stoichiometric composition CuMo₆S₈. On this basis, it was assumed that the globular formations are heterophase, in which one of the phases is CuMo₆S₈. The composition of the other phase in the globular formations should contain mainly copper.

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